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Dendrometrical structure of one fragment of the semi-deciduous seasonal forest in Brazil. Imaña, E.J. (*University of Brasilia, Brazil; jose.imana@gmail.com*).

A 10-ha semi-deciduous seasonal forest fragment (15°45'54" S and 49°04'03" W) found in the bioregion of the Savannah EcoMuseum localized in Goiás, Brazil, was studied. For the phytosociological survey, 10 sample plots of 20 × 20 m were systematically located. All living trees of 5 cm DBH and above were measured within the plot boundaries. There were 742 individuals belonging to 83 species, 67 genera, and 38 families. The richest families in terms of the number of species were Fabaceae, Rubiaceae, Myrtaceae, Apocynaceae, and Chrysobalanaceae, which contributed 48% of total species. The species with the highest importance value indices were *Tapirira guianensis* Aubl., *Protium heptaphyllum* (Aubl.) March, *Callisthene major* Mart., *Amaloua guianensis* Aubl., and *Anadenanthera macrocarpa* (Benth.) Brenan. The Shannon diversity index was 3.80 nats/individual and the Pielou equality index was 0.86. For the total population and for 25 species, 549 sampled trees had DBH values lower than 30cm. This indicates that this forest has a high potential for natural succession. Two DBH distributions were observed: the typical reversed "J", described frequently in the literature, and a nearly Gaussian distribution.

Effects of cutting intensity on regeneration of natural spruce-fir conifer and broadleaved mixed forest in Changbai Mountain. Kang, X.G., Gong, Z.W., Zhang, Q. (*Beijing Forestry University, China; xingangk@163.com; gozewe@126.com; zhangq@bjfu.edu.cn*).

For natural forests, the quantity, quality, and structure of forest regeneration varies with the cutting intensity and with the spatial pattern of the harvested trees. This study was carried out in mixed spruce-fir conifer and broadleaved forest on Changbai Mountain, Jingouling Forest Farm, in northeast China. In the 36.5 hectare forest area, a 3.4-km × 20-m sample strip was established. In this strip, there were 76 sampled forest gaps, which were classified into 10 types according to the gap size. The numbers of regenerated seedlings were measured in each gap and also under forest canopies (i.e., as understory trees). This survey showed that the number of regenerated seedlings was highest for forest gaps of 20 to 40 m², and lowest for gaps larger than 300 m². More regeneration occurred in forest gaps than under a forest canopy. Also, for fir (*Abies nephrolepis* Maxim) seedlings less than 20 years old, diameter and height growth in forest gaps was faster than under forest canopies. However, there were no significant differences in diameter and height growth in forest gaps versus under forest canopies for spruce (*Picea koraiensis* Nakai) and Korean pine (*Pinus koraiensis* Sieb. et Zucc).

Forest bark structure: an indicator of forest biodiversity and health. MacFarlane, D.W. (*Michigan State University, USA; macfar24@msu.edu*), Luo, A. (*Xishuangbanna National Nature Reserve Management Bureau, China; roger_aidong@yahoo.com.cn*).

A number of case studies have examined the important contribution of tree bark structure to the success and diversity of bark-using organisms, but methods to quantify bark structure as a component of total forest structure are lacking. Tree bark structure has also been linked to tree vigor; thus, metrics defining forest bark structure should also help to quantify forest health and inform forest ecosystem management practices. A new metric, a bark fissure index (BFI), was developed and applied to hardwood tree populations, comprising 15 different tree species common to northeastern North American forests, to examine allometric relationships among tree size, species, and bark structure. A study of the behavior of *Sitta carolinensis*, a bark-using bird species, revealed a strong correlation between BFI and bird tree-species preference. Both models and data from several sources were applied to examine species contributions to forest bark structure, revealing that species contribute unequally and predictably to forest bark structure. Variations in bark structure not explained by species composition and forest size structure are most likely explained by differences in stand age and vigor.

Stand structure classification to facilitate modelling and mapping of forest succession. Moss, I. (*Tesera Systems Inc., Canada; forestree@shaw.ca*).

A new clustering algorithm was developed to separate stands into structure classes. The clustering method maximally differentiates stands using a new measure of similarity based on empirical cumulative diameter distributions. The overall goal was to develop a high-level standardized system of classification to facilitate more consistent, precise, reliable, and verifiable communications across disciplines. This system was also designed to connect tree, stand, and forest-level dynamics. The resulting stand structure classes can be used for a number of applications, such as growth modelling, habitat assessment, and relating stand structure to fuel loading and non-timber forest products (NTFPs). In this paper, the use of the stand structure classification system to characterize stand succession over time and to summarize the extent of each class over a landscape is discussed. The clustering algorithm was applied to 421 plots established in a wide variety of stand conditions in the central interior of British Columbia, Canada, resulting in a 17-class stand structure classification system. The change in stand structure classes over time was also studied within the context of delineating forest succession pathways.

Diversity of non-timber products of the Sal (*Shorea robusta* C.F. Gaertn) forests of Bangladesh. Rahman, M. (*Office of the Deputy Commissioner, Bangladesh; mizan_peraj@yahoo.com*), Vacik, H. (*University of Natural Resources and Applied Life Sciences, Austria; harald.vacik@boku.ac.at*).

Non-timber forest products (NTFPs) encompass all biological materials other than timber. NTFPs have attracted considerable global interest because of their increasing role in improving rural livelihoods. NTFPs of sal (*Shorea robusta* C.F. Gaertn) forests are important to rural people in terms of foods, medicines, fodder, and domestic requirements in the central part of Bangladesh. Species composition, richness, and diversity of NTFPs—including mushrooms, herbs, climbers, and shrubs—were compared between unmanaged (natural, mixed tree species) and successional (pure species, regenerated naturally after clear cutting) stands of Madhupur sal forests. The main results were: (i) unmanaged stands showed higher species richness than successional stands; (ii) species richness of edible and medicinal plants increased with decreased canopy closure in unmanaged stands; (iii) species richness and abundances of medicinal and edible climbers were higher in mixed species stands compared to the pure sal stands; and (iv) species richness and abundance of mushrooms increased with increasing sal tree age. Based on the study, a sustainable management approach that protects the floral diversity of the ecosystem over the long run is recommended. Also, understanding and incorporating local knowledge about conservation of forest resources is essential to sustainable forest management.